

VETERINARY SCIENCES

FEEDING MULBERRY SILKWORMS WITH AUTUMN LEAF EXTRACTS

Atayeva V.,

ANAS Sheki Regional Scientific Center, researcher, dissertate

Salmanova A.,

ANAS Sheki Regional Scientific Center, researcher, dissertate

Shukurlu Yu.,

ANAS Sheki Regional Scientific Center, director, PhD

Valibeyov Kh.

ANAS Sheki Regional Scientific Center, researcher

Abstract

Because of their high amount of biologically active compounds, anthocyanins are a phenolic compound known not only as food but also for their use in modern medicine. In this study, the effects of autumn leaf extracts of *Amaranthus* (*Amaranthus*) and *Cotinus coggygria* (*Cotinus coggygria* L.) rich in anthocyanins on the biology of mulberry silkworm were investigated in a non-laboratory setting. Autumn leaf extracts of *Amaranth* and *Cotinus coggygria* were heated at 60⁰ °C in different proportions for 90 min. and extracted by brewing in water. Mulberry leaves were used for feeding silkworms after being soaked with autumn leaf extract prepared in ratios of 1:3, 1:1, and 3:1. The results showed that silkworms fed with autumn leaf extracts had improved silk production biology and higher survival. 1:1 concentration of the extract gave the best results.

Keywords: autumn leaves, anthocyanin, amaranth, *Cotinus coggygria*, silkworm.

INTRODUCTION

Silk has a long history of use as a suture material in the medical field due to its mechanical properties, adaptability, and flexibility [1]. Therefore, one of the most urgent issues is the preparation and increase of natural biomaterials in economically efficient and convenient ways. For this reason, various studies have been conducted to increase productivity in silk production. Egyptian researchers found the optimal concentration to be 50% in their studies of mulberry juice feeding. They concluded that feeding with 25–50% concentrated mulberry fruit juice was more important than the control [2, 3]. The effect of feeding with folic acid on the development of silkworms and cocoons was studied, and high economic results were obtained [4,5].

Autumn leaves are one of the natural sources of antioxidants, rich in anthocyanins due to their phenolic content. Anthocyanins are substances sensitive to environmental pH, temperature, light, oxygen, and metal ions [6]. In the presented study, the efficacy of *Bombyx mori* L. fed with mulberry leaves supplemented with autumn leaf extract rich in anthocyanins was tested. The effect of such feeding on some biological aspects of the silkworm has been observed.

Extraction of autumn leaves and extract: Collected, dried to a constant weight at 50⁰ °C, and then crushed purple-red autumn leaves (sorrel and amaranth) were poured into 300-ml chemical beakers, then distilled water was added in different solid-liquid ratios (1:3, 1:1, 3:1) and brewed at 60⁰ °C for 90 minutes. Centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min, collected separately in brown bottles, and stored in the refrigerator.

EXPERIMENT AND METHOD

The mulberry silkworm used in this study is a native species of the *Bombyx mori* family, ShZEM-4. Larvae were reared in separate containers under non-laboratory conditions at 23 ± 5 °C and provided with appropriate amounts of fresh mulberry leaves. After the third sleep, the feeding, growth, and productivity performance of silkworms on extract-soaked mulberry

leaves were investigated using standard methods widely used in sericulture. Initially, the larvae were divided into 4 groups of 1 mg. With every feeding, mulberry leaves soaked in extracts containing significant anthocyanins were supplied. After the worms knitted the cocoons, they were killed in a thermostat at 60⁰ °C. After this, measurements were obtained.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After the experiments and analysis, the 1:1 ratio concentration compared to others was considered the optimal level due to the development of caterpillars and the increase in the weight of cocoons and pupae. The productivity and survival of silkworms fed with mulberry leaves with amaranth extract (Figure 1) were higher than those of silkworms fed with mulberry leaves with *Cotinus coggygria* leaf extract (Figure 2). This is also associated with vitamin C in amaranth extract [7].

The cocoon, cocoon shell weight, and productivity were lower in all experimental groups when fed with a concentrated solution in the ratio of 3:1. This is related to the stickiness of the solution with a high concentration of the extract.

The presented work showed that a 1:1 extract solution can promote the growth of caterpillars and pupae of the local silkworm species *Bombyx mori* ShZEM-4, and these cocoons are more productive and have a significant impact on overall productivity; although, the high concentration (3:1) had an adverse effect on the activity of the silkworm. The results of the biological and technological indicators obtained are listed in Table 1.

It can be seen from Table 1 that the average mass of dry cocoon, the yield of raw silk in dry cocoon, and the average length of the cocoon stalk indicators are maximum relatively 0.66 mg, 35,7 %, 910-950 m when silkworms were fed leaves soaked with 1:1 amaranth extract compared with control.

Table 1.

Technological indicators of the cocoon

Indicators	control	Saragan			Amaranth		
		3:1	1:1	1:3	3:1	1:1	1:3
Average mass of dry cocoon, mg	0,57	0,59	0,63	0,51	0,61	0,66	0,53
Yield of raw silk in dry cocoon, %	33,3	33,8	34,6	29,2	34,01	35,7	30,2
The average length of the cocoon stalk, m	850-900	865-910	900-930	810-850	880-920	910-950	830-870

Figure 1. Silkworms feeding on amaranth extract

Figure 2. Silkworms feeding with saragan extract

It is well known that one of the primary determinants of silkworm growth and development is temperature and relative humidity [8,9,10]. The Sheki region of Azerbaijan experiences a monthly relative humidity

of $60 \pm 5\%$ during the day and $65 \pm 5\%$ at night; however, the extracts applied to the leaves maintain a normal relative humidity, preventing the leaves from drying out too rapidly (Table 2).

Table 2.

Influence of extracts on T and RH factors in June

Condition factors	Incubation	I instar	II instar	III instar	IV instar	V instar	Spinning
Temperature	22-26°C	22-25°C	23-26°C	23-27°C	24-28°C	23-26°C	24-28°C
Relative humidity	73-78%	73-76%	72-75%	72-75%	72-74%	71-73%	70-72%
Relative humidity (control)	62-65%	60-63%	60-62%	59-61%	59-62%	58-60%	57-60%

CONCLUSION

Studies have shown that silkworms fed leaves soaked with amaranth plant extract were more productive than silkworms fed leaves soaked with *Cotinus coggygia* plant extract. In addition to this, extracts with water provide the required temperature and relative humidity for optimal conditions, so high-quality silkworms are obtained. This method affords the breeding of silkworms in the hot months of the year.

References

- Islam M. S., Rahman S. Temperature and Relative Humidity-Mediated Immature Development and Adult Emergence in the Mulberry Silkworm *Bombyx mori* L., *Elixir International Journal*, 118, 2018
- Jiménez A., Dulce M., Grusak M.A. (2017). Minerals, vitamin C, phenolics, flavonoids, and antioxidant activity of *Amaranthus* leafy vegetables. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 58, 33–39. doi:10.1016/j.jfca.2017.01.005.
- Khamenei T., Ali S., Sendi, Jalal J., Imaani S. Shojae M., Nielsen A. (2019). Can Feeding of Silkworms on Different Mulberry Variety Affect Its

Performance?. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, toz229-. doi:10.1093/jee/toz229

- Mubashar H., Muhammad N., Shakil A.K., Muhammad F.B., Muhammad M. Studies on the influence of temperature and humidity on biological traits of silkworm (*Bombyx mori* L.; *Bombycidae*), *African Journal of Biotechnology* Vol. 10(57), pp. 12368-12375, 28 September 2011, DOI: 10.5897/AJB11.1805

- Mubashar H., Shakil Ahmad K., Muhammad N., Farooq N. Effect of Rearing Temperature and Humidity on Fecundity and Fertility of Silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L. (*Lepidoptera: Bombycidae*), *Pakistan J. Zool.*, vol. 43(5), pp. 979-985, 2011.

- Rahmathulla V.K., Das P., Ramesh M., Rajan R.K.. Growth rate pattern and economic traits of silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L under the influence of folic acid administration. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage.* December, 2007 Vol. 11(4) 81 – 84

- Rateb S.H., Abdel-Rahman Y.A. Effects of some Extracts on Growth Characters of Mulberry Silkworm "*Bombyx mori* L." *Assiut Journal of Agricultural Sciences*. Page 71-58

8. Saad I. A. I. Using the mulberry fruit extract for improving silk production of mulberry silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L. *Journal of Plant Protection and Pathology, Egypt*. Article 3, Volume 4, Issue 11, November 2013, Page 927-932
9. Verbeyst L., Oey I., I. Van der P., Hendrickx M., Van Loey A. Kinetic study on the thermal and pressure degradation of anthocyanins in strawberries, *Food Chem.* 123 (2) (2010) 269-27
10. Yumin Y., Xuemei C., Fei D., Peiyun Z., Jie L., Xiaosong G.. (2007). Biocompatibility evaluation of silk fibroin with peripheral nerve tissues and cells in vitro. 28(9), 1643–1652. doi:10.1016/j.biomaterials.2006.12.004